

Improving the Management of Construction and Demolition Waste in Middle East

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

making framework for enhancing CDW management in UAE urban redevelopment projects at the district level. The research will look at the critical aspects to consider and determine the data needed to help CDW management make decisions that balance environmental, economic, and social goals.

1.2 Research Background

Over the last century, rapid population increase and urbanization have had a profound impact on urban

ABSTRACT

Rising population and urbanization have had a substantial influence on aging urban infrastructure in both developed and developing countries during the last three decades. As a result, in many cities around the world, sustainable urban rebuilding has become a key approach. As a result, policymakers have made it a priority to plan well for building and demolition waste management practices. Due to a growing awareness of sustainable construction methods in the Middle East, urban redevelopment projects are now obliged to be delivered in a sustainable manner. However, demolition waste management has yet to be effective due to a lack of understanding of how a sustainability policy is applied in practice, as well as a lack of expertise and information available to project stakeholders on demolition trash management. In this context, this study creates a decision-making framework with important decision-making elements and a database to aid in the demolition waste management decision-making process in urban redevelopment projects.

Keywords: CONSTRUCTION WASTE; DEMOLITION WASTE; FRAMEWORK; CDW

1. Introduction

1.1 Aim of the Research

The purpose of this research is to create a complete decision-

infrastructure. Urban redevelopment has become inescapable in the process of urban change, which is a key problem in both theory and practice. To enhance living conditions and infrastructure, several cities throughout the world are undergoing large-scale housing and urban redevelopment initiatives. Urban redevelopment is regarded a challenging subject [1] because of the vast number of players, the financial investment necessary, and the influence on society and the environment. Urban redevelopment has received a lot of attention in recent years in both industrialized and developing countries, resulting in a flurry of studies [2]. In order to balance the economic, social, and environmental challenges that arise as a result of rebuilding, researchers have been focusing increasingly on sustainable urban redevelopment.

CDW issues have been related to urban redevelopment in a many of nations, including Hong Kong, the United States, and the United Kingdom [3]. Rapid urban growth in Hong Kong, for example, has resulted in overflowing landfills. An estimated 2.8 million dwelling units in the United States were demolished in the 2010s, resulting in a large quantity of CDW. However, researchers and practitioners in underdeveloped nations have paid less attention to the topic of urban redevelopment CDW management.

The UAE has also had to cope with difficulties related to urban redevelopment. Many cities in the United Arab Emirates have experienced decades of rapid urbanization and population increase. In addition, the desire to improve urban life has supported the redevelopment of many historic city areas. Old structures will be removed in huge numbers to make way for new developments, according to the UAE's urban regeneration initiatives. This demands CDW management, which occurs during the demolition process.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Lifecycle of The Built Environment

The concept of a closed loop in the building sector is based on natural ecology [4]. Because buildings are formed of the complexity of natural elements with their own life spans, such as wood, steel, concrete, polymers, and ceramics, building development is seen as a cyclical process that consumes a considerable amount of energy and materials. The quality of the components, the intended usage, the environment, and the socioeconomic status all factor into whether or not a structure will last a long time.

Figure 1: A CDW management framework.

The construction lifetime refers to the process of planning, development, design, use, maintenance, and demolition. According to the C&D waste management paradigm, Figure 1 [5] depicts the six stages of a project lifetime, from concept to design, construction, and operation, to maintenance and destruction. As demonstrated, the destruction and redevelopment stages are linked, and the life cycle of the building is finished at the demolition stage. At the end of a building's life cycle, demolition is thought to produce more garbage than the other stages.

In the field of construction, academics and practitioners are striving to develop alternatives to demolition and environmental consequences, such as maintenance or deconstruction of existing structures, in order to extend the life of buildings and avoid destruction and environmental problems. It is argued that deconstruction, rather than destruction and construction of new buildings, is a more sustainable strategy. The quantity of garbage generated during demolition and the reuse of existing structures can both be reduced with this strategy.

2.2 Waste Management in Construction Industry

CDW refers to solid waste generated during the construction, renovation, and demolition of structures. These structures include all forms of buildings, both residential and non-residential, as well as roadways and bridges. Construction waste, rehabilitation waste, and demolition waste are the three categories of CDW based on the stages of production.

In the 1980s, the term "integrated" was coined in the waste management industry, and by the mid-2010s,

it had become standardized. The three triple bottom line objectives of sustainability that must be highlighted in an integrated solid waste management method are economic, environmental, and social aspects of sustainability. In addition, political, economic, socioeconomic, and environmental factors must be considered by the government and local governments. In the literature and in practice, integrated waste management is characterized as a strategy for accomplishing sustainability goals. This is standard practice across the board, including in CDW management. A conceptual model of building waste management in achieving sustainability has been presented, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Conceptual model for sustainable construction waste management

As a result, if a comprehensive strategy and solution based on the interconnections between the three pillars is proposed, integrated CDW management can only be realized. The system's complexity in identifying integrated CDW management is depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: System for integrated demolition waste management

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Approach

This research takes a practical approach. The research process is said to have become more flexible and straightforward as a result of this strategy. This comprises a range of methods for determining the best answers

to the research questions. In order to establish or test a research theory, the research approach specifies how to approach data collecting and analysis. This study uses both inductive and deductive methodologies at different phases of the research process. Deductive research creates a hypothesis with the objective of subjecting it to a rigorous test, whereas inductive research builds a theory based on diverse observations.

Combining quantitative and qualitative data might serve to create a more full picture of the phenomenon, according to the differences between quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods research. As a result of adopting mixed techniques, the researcher can get insight into the research challenges and efficiently address the research questions. As a result, it's crucial to fully understand the factors that drive decision-making. To explore the perspectives of stakeholders, identify crucial decision-making elements, and construct a supporting database, quantitative methodologies must be applied.

3.2 Research Method

Because the study's purpose is to provide a decision-making framework for better CDW management in urban redevelopment projects, a hybrid method of qualitative and quantitative data collecting, and analysis is needed to discover the important aspects influencing DW management. A decision support system based on GIS technologies is also presented as a supporting database in the decision-making process. Qualitative and quantitative methodologies can be integrated in a variety of ways depending on the study objectives. To answer the research questions, quantitative and qualitative approaches are combined, appropriate research methods are chosen, and a logical research process is formalized. The four main research methodologies used in this study were literature reviews, questionnaire surveys, interviews, and case studies.

4. Analysis and Discussions

4.1 Concept Based Framework

A review of the literature on urban redevelopment, the relationship between sustainability and urban redevelopment, CDW management, the context of CDW management in UAE urban redevelopment, and organizational decision-making were all conducted as part of the research. This offered useful information for researching domains of information needed to establish research gaps and factors impacting DW management decision-making in urban redevelopment projects, which was used to build the conceptual framework. To be more precise, study gaps shown that there are various obstacles in managing urban redevelopment CDW due to the complexities involved, such as inefficient waste management planning, overlapping of tasks, and ineffective time and cost management. As a result, successful waste management demands a well-defined decision-making process including important stakeholders, as well as project performance that is sustainable.

By defining 18 themes for examination and dividing them into five categories: technical, environmental, economic, social, and institutional, the conceptual framework embeds knowledge of sustainable urban redevelopment, integrated waste management, and organizational decision-making. Decision makers can gain

a better knowledge of the factors that influence CDW management in urban redevelopment projects by analyzing the multi-criterion themes. The social sustainability of CDW management, for example, is ensured by considering natural resources and history. Urban redevelopment initiatives can also be a cause of conflict if they are badly planned.

The conceptual framework for bettering CDW management in urban redevelopment projects was created, and it includes five categories, 19 key themes, and 53 decision-making criteria that were utilized to create survey questions. These findings indicated intellectual and practical difficulties about urban redevelopment DW management, as well as decision-making variables. Developed countries, such as the United Kingdom, other European countries, and the United States, have a better grasp of CDW management in urban reconstruction, according to linked research. Graph 4.

Figure 4: Conceptual Framework

4.2 Upgraded Framework

The proposed framework was confirmed in the interview study by asking for expert comments, and the conceptual framework was revised in the survey study by examining stakeholders' perspectives. In this case, the research goal of "identifying crucial decision-making elements of CDW management in urban redevelopment projects" was met. Investigating the various concerns and expectations of key stakeholders in making decisions about CDW management in urban redevelopment; identifying the critical decision-making factors in achieving effective CDW management; and developing action plans for each critical factor to improve CDW management were three other sub-objectives central to this goal.

Figure 5: Upgraded Framework

In the survey study, 22 out of 52 decision-making elements that were determined to have an impact on CDW management in the UAE's urban redevelopment project were developed by quantitative analysis. The framework was redesigned based on 24 important elements, as shown in Figure 5. All five stakeholder groups agreed on the majority of these essential elements, while there were minor variances in importance ratings. The interviews highlighted steps taken to improve CDW management in urban redevelopment in the UAE, as well as a better understanding of the important elements. Technical performance, environmental performance, economic performance, social performance, and institutional performance were all considered while evaluating these components of sustainability.

5. End Notes

5.1 Conclusion

Urban redevelopment is a major topic around the world, especially in poor countries. As a result, for years, practitioners and academics have debated how to make CDW management decisions in urban redevelopment projects. Recent research has improved CDW management in urban redevelopment projects in

terms of decision support, environmental concerns, stakeholder participation, strategy and solution, and assessment. By integrating a supporting database with a decision-making framework to aid decision-makers in making CDW management decisions in urban redevelopment projects, the purpose of this study is to find new information and add to the current body of knowledge. The research findings were refined to construct the decision-making framework by merging the validated framework and supporting database of CDW management. From a practical aspect, the finalized decision-making framework may give comprehensive and multi-criteria references that incorporate both geographic and attribute information to decision makers in urban redevelopment CDW management at the district level.

5.2 Future

Key knowledge gaps in present research, as well as recommendations for future study, were identified under four main topics: decision support, decision-making, stakeholder engagement, and assessment. Given the complexities and limitations of applying CDW management in urban redevelopment projects, there is opportunity to learn more about these disciplines. The knowledge, insights, and recommendations aided in the establishment of a framework for critically addressing the difficulties related with CDW management in urban reconstruction to enhance urban redevelopment sustainability.

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